

Factors Affecting Reading Challenge among Intermediate Pupils in a Public School in Bulacan

Serina Amper, Angel Lhaine C. Arnado, Jonamy Buslon, Jemelyn D.C. Robles, Marielle Coleen D.R. Saguid, Joseline M. Santos, Ph.D., Richelle C. Castro, and Remelie R. Robles, Ed.D, LPT

Bulacan State University

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*Corresponding Author: Serina Amper

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Abstract

Original Research Article

This study examined the factors that contribute to reading challenges among intermediate learners in a public school in Bulacan. This study explored learner-related, home environment, parental, and teacher-related factors that contribute to reading comprehension. The researchers used a mixed-methods design, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and regression analysis to gain a comprehensive understanding of the problem. Participants for this study were from three grade levels: grades 4, 5, and 6. Learners based on purposive sampling included 150 learners, one English reading teacher, and five parents. The results showed that the majority of learners responded favorably, indicating that, at least in terms of their perceptions, supportive conditions existed in different contexts that influenced reading. However, inferential statistics showed one important finding using multiple linear regression: relatively speaking, only teacher-related factors in this context made a statistically significant positive contribution to learners' reading comprehension levels ($\beta=0.203, p=0.021$). In conclusion, several factors influence students' reading journey. However, teacher-related factors were the most common factors for intermediate learners' reading comprehension in this study. Finally, the study recommended that new interventions be trialed for any future studies that these researchers should undertake, and the socio-economic and language context of students should be considered, with larger sample sizes undertaken to improve the intervention strategies and research outcomes.

Keywords: Intermediate, Reading Challenges, Reading Proficiency, Comprehension, Home Environment.

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INTRODUCTION

Literacy skills form the foundation for every individual to learn in all areas of life. This is a means of constructing words meaningfully. Being able to read and write helps everyone communicate effectively. In daily life, communication connects individuals to understanding, accumulating information, and sharing ideas. Reading and writing open the minds of people and gain insights into diverse cultures, beliefs, traditions, and practices of the world. In school, learners acquire knowledge to become competent and skilled enough to meet basic learning standards. Reading is one of the most essential requirements and essentials of humanity since the existence and development of basic language has shown its positive effect in every aspect and moment of a

person's life (Akyol, 2016; Akyol, 2019; Bıyık & Erdoğan, 2017; Çaycı & Demir, 2006).

However, not all learners can acquire literacy skills, making it difficult for them to learn. Many students encounter difficulties reading, especially letters, syllables and sentences (Suyatno, 2022). According to the World Bank, the percentage of non-proficient children reading in the Philippines rose to 91% by 2022. Findings from the Second Congressional Commission on Education (2025) show that many Filipino students read several years below their expected reading level, highlighting the urgent need for extreme educational interventions. Meron (2018) stated that poverty is a contributing factor. Poverty, technology, and a lack of motivation and inspiration have inhibited education, particularly reading education.

In practical terms, Nurdianingsih (2021) says reading is one of four language skills and has three basic definitions where you learn to read by: (1) learning how to pronounce the words; (2) learning to identify the words and get meaning from them; and (3) learning to get meaning from the text or extract messages from a text. Taladngoen et al. (2020) also found that external factors that affect students' difficulties in reading comprehension include teachers' influence, family influence, and environment. Nevertheless, a major part of the world's population has difficulties with such basic skills. This issue, commonly referred to as poor reading comprehension, is a significant concern in educational settings worldwide (D'Angelo, N., et al. 2020; Luzano, 2020). Snow et al (2002), and Gina and Ayu (2019) described reading comprehension as a simultaneous process of extracting and constructing meaning by interacting with and engaging in written language.

This is in line with Widyaningrum et al (2020), who stated that readers must give meaning to words as they speak, listen, write, and read. Evidence showing that parental involvement may be effective in promoting positive attitudes towards reading in children who experience difficulties reading at school (Baker, 2003; Choi et al., 2022). Despite their socio-economic status, many Filipinos are unable to learn (Adapon & Mangila, 2020). Young children who are at risk of reading difficulties encounter barriers in possessing the understanding and use of foundational skills such as phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension (J. Lara, 2021). These challenges may also negatively affect self-esteem and motivation, leading to disengagement from the learning process and reduced academic achievement (Sasan & Rabillas, 2022). Children with poor language and literacy abilities are at an increased risk of long-term unemployment, lower levels of civic engagement, and dismissible life outcomes (Nag et al., 2024).

Put in a microcosm, the same alarming scenario was mirrored in the researchers' locale, where Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI SY 2019-2020) results revealed that 491 junior high school students are at the 'frustration reader' status and 41 'non-readers.' Furthermore, while previous studies have primarily focused on the association of various factors (parents, homes, teachers, and learners) with the reading comprehension level of Grade VI learners, they have not explored the specific strategies or interventions that could be implemented to enhance reading comprehension based on these identified factors. This absence indicates the need for additional research into pedagogical methods and reading materials that accommodate the varied needs of learners. While the review indicates that all the variables had a statistically significant influence on reading traits, there is limited further exploration of how the factors may interact with or deploy together to affect a learner's reading skills. Future research would benefit from stimulating consideration of how factors interact with one another, including cumulative outcomes of reading comprehension.

The purpose of this research is to address the deficits in prior research by developing useful strategies based on the researcher's completed research. Reading intervention

strategies are essential for students who struggling with reading. By using specific interventions that meet the student's requirements, there were not enough interventions shown in detail to observe how much reading was improved (Idulog et al., 2023).

This study examined the factors that affect reading comprehension among intermediate learners in a public school in Bulacan. Based on these factors, this study plans to create an intervention to assist learners in reading challenges.. Specifically, the study examined parental factors, the home environment, learner-related factors, and teacher-related factors that might influence reading skills. Ultimately, this study aims to improve reading proficiency and learning outcomes and examine whether there are any significant relationships between learner reading comprehension levels and the factors mentioned above related to reading. The study would like to make evidence-based suggestions to help learners, parents, and teachers in their reading comprehension instruction.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a mixed methods approach. It employed a convergent parallel design, which involved gathering quantitative and qualitative data simultaneously, analyzing each data type individually, and then integrating the two data sets for interpretation. According to Morse (1991), mixed methods research combines qualitative (QUAL) and quantitative (QUAN) data to generate an accurate evaluation.

The quantitative aspect of this study is a regressional type of quantitative design to determine the effects of multiple independent variables (parental factors, home environment factors, learner-related factors, and teacher-related factors) on the dependent variable (the learners' reading comprehension level). A regressional-type quantitative research design is suitable because it is designed to determine the statistical relationship and predictive power of the variables affecting learners' reading challenges. Data were collected using survey questionnaires as they are reliable and valid data sources.

The qualitative part extended the knowledge of learners' content, context, and experiences with their reading challenges. This qualitative part included interviews to gain a deeper comprehension of numbers. It was qualitative because it was based on the teacher's and parents' experiences and understandings, which could never be obtained from quantitative methods alone.

This research was conducted at a Public Elementary School in Bulacan, and focused on Grades 4 to 6 pupils who were identified as having reading difficulty. Subsequently, study respondents were selected using Phil-IRI post-conference results, specifically pupils classified as instructional and frustration-level readers. Study respondents were surveyed using questionnaires regarding various variables affecting the research questions; specifically, teachers and parents of pupils were interviewed using structured interviews to provide

contextual and narrative data to support survey questionnaire findings.

Participants

Purposive sampling was used in this study. The respondents of the study were selected as grade 4-6 pupils with reading challenges, teachers, and parents in a Public Elementary School in Bulacan. The researcher selected the respondents of the study based on the PHIL-IRI post-conference results of the pupils. Only students at frustration and instructional levels were included in the study. In addition, a teacher and five pupils' parents were interviewed to assess their influence on the reading development of the pupils and the challenges they faced. The respondents of the study were purposely chosen because the researchers believed that through this sampling, the data needed for the study were obtained. The researchers used a Raosoft calculator to determine the minimum number of samples necessary. Raosoft calculated a total sample of 208 out of 449 identified instructional and frustration levels. A total of 225 questionnaires were administered to pupils. A total of 150 participants agreed to participate in the research, and 75 disagreed.

Instruments

This research utilized Two instruments were used to gather the qualitative and quantitative data. The results of the post-test conference of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Test serve as the primary tool to measure the reading comprehension levels of selected pupils, where it categorized them as independent, instructional, and frustrated readers. An adopted survey questionnaire by Cadiong (2019) with a 5-point Likert scale was administered to Grade 4 to Grade 6 pupils, which was identified as instructional and frustrated readers to evaluate the learner-related factors, teacher-related factors, home environment factors, and influence of parental factors. A Likert scale was used to measure the level of agreement. This survey was validated by experts who considered both face and content validity in the area of education. The validity and relevance of this study were thoroughly checked and validated. Regarding the use of elementary learners as a sample of respondents, the survey was translated into Tagalog so that they could understand it better and answer it truthfully. Additionally, the researchers created structured interviews with teachers focusing on reading and some parents of pupils of selected respondents to gain insights about the strategies they used, their materials, and how they communicated the pupils' progress. This was performed with the permission of the respondents through written and recorded audio. These combined instruments ensure thorough data gathering that supports the study of a mixed-method approach.

Procedure

The following steps were undertaken to collect data. The first step the researchers do is to personally deliver an approval and permission letter requesting the administration of a Public Elementary School in Bulacan to conduct a research

study. Once permission was granted, the researchers identified the participants through the PHIL-IRI post-test results of the pupils who were identified as having instructional and frustration levels in comprehension.

After identifying the participants, a student assent form and parental consent form were provide to ensure that they were willing to allow their children to participate in the study, as well as informed consent for one (1) teacher and selected parents. Throughout this research, ethical considerations were of utmost importance.

The participants were given information about the study's goals, procedures, and confidentiality. For student assent, the form was written at an age-appropriate reading level, and parental and/or teacher consent was obtained for the relevant aspects of the study. The research team ensured the confidentiality and anonymity of any data in which identifying aspects were completely and intentionally removed during the analysis and secure data storage. The research design was also thoughtfully aware of minimizing potential harm and to maximizing potential benefits. Specifically, the instruments used for data collection were developed and designed to reduce damage while optimizing benefits. During the interviewing phase, respectful interviewing was a part of the process. Researchers were committed to ensuring the dignity and care of all participants, and there was an awareness of linguistic diversity for participants interviewed in Tagalog or or concerns about linguistic differences within the participants' completed questionnaires. Data accuracy and integrity were obtained through consultation and validation of data collection instruments by experts in the research project area, and by ensuring careful and diligent analysis. By adhering to these ethical concerns, this study was informed of ways to afford respect to respondents' rights and welfare.

Subsequently, an assent form was collected, and once the participants who agreed were identified, the questionnaires were translated into Tagalog and validated by our validator to ensure the participants' comprehension. The survey administration was then conducted by providing a Tagalog Likert-scale questionnaire to the students to assess various factors affecting reading challenges. Additionally, interviews were conducted to , gather qualitative data through structured interviews with teachers focused on reading and five (5) selected parents. Finally, the process involved collecting and tabulating all recorded interviews into text, and all responses were organized for analysis. These procedures ensured that our data were accurate, reliable, and relevant to the current study.

Data Analysis

Data collected by the researchers from the survey questionnaires and interviews were tabulated and organized. The mean and standard deviation were used to interpret the responses of the diverse learners. The data were subjected to statistical analysis to answer the questions proposed in this study. Moreover, the statistical treatments that the researchers used in the study were descriptive statistics and regression

analysis to measure the impact of factors affecting the reading comprehension of the pupils, such as parental, home environment, learner-related, and teacher-related factors. This study focuses on the factors that affect the reading challenges of intermediate learners and influence their reading progress. By determining their responses, the researchers developed an action plan that could potentially benefit both the teachers and learners. Additionally, inductive coding analysis is used by the researchers in the coding process of thematic analysis to effectively organize and interpret data. This process involved organizing themes of information gathered from structured interviews conducted to gather qualitative data from parents and a teacher. Moreover, the researchers used in vivo methods to organize and interpret the data obtained from structured

interviews with the teacher. This process used the participants' own words as codes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Level of Reading Comprehension Based on the Results of Phil-IRI Post-Conference

The initial inquiry of this study intended to gauge the extent of intermediate learners' reading comprehension as measured by the Phil-IRI test. Descriptive statistics for reading comprehension levels, categorized instructional levels, and frustration levels are displayed in Table 3.

Comprehension Level	Frequency	Percentage
Instructional (1)	87	58.00%
Frustration (2)	63	42.00%
TOTAL	150	100.00%

Table 1 presents the distribution of learners according to their comprehension level (Phil-IRI post-conference results). It registered an overall total of 150 respondents, resulting in instructional and frustration-level readers. This was measured using the Phil-IRI Post-Conference Results. This shows that most learners or 58.00%, were at the instructional level. Moreover, 42.00% of the learners were at frustration level. This means that most learners' reading comprehension is at the instructional level, meaning that they can understand and engage with the material. These learners can comprehend text with guidance, meaning that they have a strong foundation in reading skills but may need some advice for a deeper understanding of the content. According to Saaris (2019), the impetus to promote more equity among learners resulted in the development of a Mixed-Ability Classroom. The mixed-ability classroom approach aims to provide access to high-quality instruction and resources regardless of background and ability. Reading becomes enjoyable when readers communicate their understanding and ideas with the text (Reader's Handbook, 2020).

In the same table, 63 (42.00%) of the learners were at the frustration level, which means that the material was too challenging to understand independently. These readers have difficulty understanding the text even with additional support. They struggle to read at the grade level and experience anxiety and sadness while in school. Usually, it is the thing that underlies a child's inability to actively engage with the material to make sense of it that causes reading and understanding challenges (Mind Champs, 2018; Oxford Learning, 2019). Wang et al. (2020) argued that reading can attentively measure students' new learning, meaning new knowledge; therefore,

reading must allow students to use adaptable reading processes and motivations to discover and learn more. Reading hardships at the frustration/academic-stagnation level may lead to disenfranchised education, and learners living at this level will struggle to understand and develop opposition to reading and learning. Furthermore, reading understanding outcomes could be independent of what creates reading challenges; these reading comprehension issues will be less in nature than learners' knowledge acquisition unless poor study habits and negative learning dispositions lead misshapen knowledge acquisition to a lesser degree (Casinillo, 2019; Tavera & Casinillo, 2020).

Phil-IRI post-conference data from 150 respondents; the results in Table 1 indicate a remarkable gap in learners' reading comprehension skills. Many learners (58%) were at the instructional level, meaning that they required some guidance to understand the text. However, 42% were at the frustration level, which is disturbing because many learners cannot understand the material even when help is provided. This calls for differentiated instructions to accommodate the group's needs. Instructional level learners have some understanding of reading but require additional support to comprehend well, while frustration level learners are in significant difficulty, which affects their academic performance.

The high percentage of frustrated readers indicates that some attention may be required. These learners struggle to make sense of the text, which may harm their health and attitude towards studying. They understood that comprehension requires material engagement, which these learners currently lack.

2. Factors Contributing to Reading Challenges

An analysis of the factors contributing to reading challenges was conducted using quantitative measures. The

following factors were examined: parental, home environment, learner-related, and teacher-related factors.

2.1

Table 2. *Descriptive Measure of the Extent of Parental Factors on the Reading Comprehension Level of Pupils with Reading Challenges*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Give sufficient educational support and concern for my studies.	4.64	0.76	Strongly Agree	To a Very Great Extent
2. Provide proper nourishment needed for my studies.	4.73	0.60	Strongly Agree	To a Very Great Extent
3. Obtain the necessary physical needs for me.	4.36	0.89	Agree	To a Great Extent
4. Reward me whenever I obtain high grades.	3.72	1.20	Agree	To a Great Extent
5. Keep me away from family problems and frequent quarrels.	3.77	1.47	Agree	To a Great Extent
6. Praise me for any success I achieve in school.	4.27	1.03	Agree	To a Great Extent
7. Listen to my explanations before scolding or disciplining me.	3.99	1.34	Agree	To a Great Extent
8. Involve themselves in improving my reading skills.	4.40	1.01	Agree	To a Great Extent
9. Assist me in preparing my homework.	4.01	1.32	Agree	To a Great Extent
10. Communicate with me regularly regarding my studies.	4.16	1.16	Agree	To a Great Extent
11. Encourage me to stay at home and study instead of going elsewhere.	4.33	0.89	Agree	To a Great Extent
12. Attend to my emotional, social, intellectual, and health needs.	4.4	0.96	Agree	To a Great Extent
OVERALL	4.23	0.45	Agree	To a Great Extent

Table 2 shows the students' perspectives regarding their parents' involvement in their reading progress. The pupils were asked to rate each statement from 1 to 5 based on a scale indicating the extent of parents' participation or involvement. In this table, a higher mean suggests that pupils recognize that their parents are highly involved in their reading progress. At the same time, the standard deviation indicated that the lower the SD, the higher the agreement among the pupils, and the higher the SD, the lower the agreement of the pupils.

The data suggest that, on average, students with reading challenges mostly "agree" that their parents are highly involved in their reading progress. The overall mean of 4.23 falls in the "Agree" range, interpreted as "To a Great Extent." Indicators 2 and 1 are the highest-rated indicators, with a mean above 4.5. Indicator 2 shows that students strongly agree that their parents give them basic nutritional needs for studying. In contrast, indicator 1 shows that pupils strongly agree that their parents give sufficient educational support and concern in their studies. Research has also shown that the best predictor of achievement for pupils is not parental income or social status; rather, it is the extent to which parents can create a home environment that supports learning, set high yet reasonable expectations for achievement and future careers, and get involved in their children's education at the school and community level (Lara and Saracostti, 2019).

In general, for high-rated indicators with a mean above 4.0, pupils agree that their parents are involved in helping them with their reading progress. Their parents attended to their overall well-being. Encourage them to stay at home and read. Provide

them with their physical needs. Give praise when they have academic achievements. Communicate with them about their homework and assist them in doing so. Reading can foster children's interest in literacy, while high-quality reading interactions with parents can help foster even better relationships between parents and children (Canfield et al., 2020) and children's more generalized engagement with reading (Reese et al., 2022).

Lower-rated indicators with a mean below 4.0 but still in the range of "Agree" and "To a Great Extent." However, for indicator 7, the results suggest that pupils are slightly less likely to strongly agree that their parents hear their explanations before disciplining them. Indicator 5 shows that students agreed, but less firmly, that they were kept away from arguments or issues in the family. Lastly, indicator 4 shows that pupils agree but still indicate that rewards, when they have good grades, are less consistently happening. Ribeiro et al. (2021) indicated that parental engagement is primarily considered as participation at home (or home-based engagement), because it is perceived as parents' participation and behavior toward their children's school life and home-learning activities related to schooling (e.g. parents helping their children with homework, parents talking to children about schooling, and parental monitoring of school work and rule-setting), participation with the school (or school-based engagement) related to the different forms of parents' participation in the school's activities, and recognize both contexts for the analysis of engagement behaviors and activities; and other forms of home-school communication, such as parents communicating with teachers.

2.2

Table 3. *Descriptive Measure of the Extent of Home Environment Factors on the Reading Comprehension Level of Pupils with Reading Challenges*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Provides for my study needs.	4.65	0.74	Strongly Agree	To a Very Great Extent
2. Has tables, chairs, lighting, and ventilation to encourage studying.	4.56	0.94	Strongly Agree	To a Very Great Extent
3. Is free from excessive noise and disturbances.	3.62	1.34	Agree	To a Great Extent
4. Has a small family size, minimizing disruptions to my studies.	3.78	1.25	Agree	To a Great Extent
OVERALL	4.15	0.63	Agree	To a Great Extent

Table 3 presents the extent to which home environment factors affect the reading comprehension level of students with reading challenges. The four indicators assess the home environment factors in the reading challenges of grades 4-6 pupils in the CMDJMCS. The overall mean was 4.15, indicating a large extent, while the standard deviation was 0.63.

In the same table, indicator 1, "Provides for my study needs," obtained the highest mean score of 4.65. This high average indicates a strong consensus among students that their home environments sufficiently support their study needs. Moreover, with a low SD (0.74), the pupils agreed that they were meeting their needs for their study at home. A study by Librea et al. (2023) emphasized that parents influence the reading ability of their children by providing for their child at home, including shared reading habits and access to various books and technology that serve as reading materials, which significantly influences learners' reading abilities. Arandas (2023) also emphasized that a supportive home environment involving parental support in reading-related activities and parental reinforcement or praise for reading will significantly affect children's reading performance development.

Additionally, indicator 2, "Has tables, chairs, lighting, and ventilation to encourage studying," also showed a high mean,

obtaining 4.65 and an SD of 0.94. This means that the pupils strongly agreed on having proper ventilation at home, providing them with a space to study that has a table, chair, and lighting that encourages them to study. However, indicator 3, "Is free from excessive noise and disturbances," and indicator 4, "Has a small family size, minimizing disruptions to my studies," show much lower means, which obtain 3.62 with an SD of 1.34 for indicator 3 and 3.78 means and 1.25 SD for indicator 4, compared to indicators 1 and 2, the last two questions obtained lower means, which means that even if they have a high agreement on receiving their needs and space for reading and learning, there are still other factors at home that hinder the pupils from improving their reading skills. As pupils, they should receive sufficient improvement not only in reading, but also in their academic performance. Home Environment is just one factor that affects learners' reading. Thus, parents can have a positive relationship with their children's literacy skills by providing an engaging activity, encouraging them to read, and supporting their literacy knowledge acquisition at home. This positive reinforcement enhances the relationship between parents and children and can also enhance children's academic achievements (Dong et al., 2020).

2.3

Table 4. *Descriptive Measure of the Extent of Learner-Related Factors on the Reading Comprehension Level of Pupils with Reading Challenges*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Receive proper motivation to read printed materials.	4.87	0.42	Strongly Agree	To a Very Great Extent
2. Can cope with and understand the lessons in reading.	4.43	0.81	Agree	To a Great Extent
3. I am prepared before engaging in reading activities.	4.33	0.91	Agree	To a Great Extent
4. Have enough low-level reading materials for practice.	4.19	1.09	Agree	To a Great Extent
OVERALL	4.46	0.49	Agree	To a Great Extent

Table 4 presents the results of learner-related factors that influence reading comprehension among instructional and frustrated readers of grades 4 to 6. Using a 5-point Likert scale, the four indicators were assessed to understand their effect on reading development. Overall, students indicated a positive perception of their feeling supported in improving their reading skills, with scores averaging 4.46. If the individual indicator

were examined, the students showed significant variability, as evidenced by standard deviation.

The highest mean score (4.87) with a low standard deviation (0.42) in the table was obtained from the indicator assessing the motivation to read printed materials. This indicates a high degree of consensus among the respondents, which supports

the assertion that motivation plays a vital role in reading achievement. Toste et al. (2020) conducted a meta-analytic review that found a strong correlation between reading motivation and reading achievement among K-12 students. Their findings revealed that motivated learners actively engaged with texts, leading to better comprehension.

In contrast, the scores for coping with reading lessons (average 4.43, SD = 0.81) and preparedness for reading activities (average 4.33, SD = 0.91) implied that students' experiences were inconsistent. Manuas et al. (2020) Support the significance of reading motivation in preparedness for reading activities. They found that learners' reading motivation significantly affected their willingness to participate in the reading tasks. Given that preparedness requires motivation

and external support, the findings suggest that improving learners' motivation to read can boost their readiness to join and engage in reading activities, which can help them develop an understanding of a lesson.

Finally, low-level reading materials obtained the lowest mean score (4.19) with a standard deviation of (1.09) in the table. This indicator indicates that while the pupils agree that reading materials that are appropriate in difficulty are available, at high standard deviation indicates considerable variability in participation. This corroborates the results of Cadiong (2019), who indicated that when reading materials are not available to pupils with appropriate difficulty, it can hinder the literacy development of the pupils.

2.4

Table 5. Descriptive Measure of the Extent of Teacher-Related Factors on the Reading Comprehension Level of Pupils with Reading Challenges

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Has time to supervise my reading progress.	4.55	0.97	Strongly Agree	To a Very Great Extent
2. Provides enough materials for students with reading difficulties.	4.59	0.71	Strongly Agree	To a Very Great Extent
3. Balances focus on both struggling readers and regular workload.	4.69	0.65	Strongly Agree	To a Very Great Extent
4. Utilizes different teaching methods and strategies.	4.45	0.89	Agree	To a Great Extent
5. Demonstrates patience when handling students with reading difficulties.	4.57	0.90	Strongly Agree	To a Very Great Extent
6. Has received sufficient training in managing students with various reading challenges.	4.71	0.70	Strongly Agree	To a Very Great Extent
OVERALL	4.60	0.52	Strongly Agree	To a Very Great Extent

Table 5 presents the extent of teacher-related factors affecting the reading comprehension level of pupils with reading challenges. It registered an overall mean of 4.60 with an SD of 0.52. Moreover, the data strongly indicates that teacher-related factors significantly and positively influence the reading comprehension of students with reading challenges, as evidenced by the consistently high mean scores across all assessed areas. Teacher-related factors are very important regarding the students' performance. Students' performance depends mainly on the teacher and what they teach in class or school. Teachers are defenders of student's performance. Teachers' poor preparation, lack of interest, and commitment to their duties are essential for the students and schools (Ullah & Almani, 2022).

In the same table, indicator 6, the highest-rated indicator, is that the teacher has received sufficient training in managing students with various readings, with a mean score of 4.71 and an SD of 0.70, with the interpretation of To a Very Great Extent. This means that teachers are perceived as being well-prepared and effective in managing the needs of struggling and regular students. Several studies have pointed out the vital role of teachers in fostering quality education and determining students' future (Chachar, Ullah, and Ujjan, 2023). Teachers are believed to be well prepared to deal with pupils with reading

challenges. Additionally, indicator 3 is the high-rated indicator that balances focus on struggling readers and regular workload, with a mean of 4.69 and SD of 0.65 with the interpretation of To a Very Great Extent. Students recognize their teachers as well-trained to manage an extensive number of reading problems and are capable of balancing the needs of struggling readers with a regular classroom workload.

Moreover, indicator 2 provides enough materials for students with reading challenges, with a mean score of 4.59 and an SD of 0.71, with the interpretation of To a very Great Extent. This means that students perceive their teachers as consistently providing sufficient materials to address their reading challenges. Furthermore, indicator 5 demonstrates patience when handling students with reading challenges, with a mean score of 4.57 and an SD of 0.90 with the interpretation of To a Very Great Extent. This means that students feel that their teachers give them plenty of the right materials to help them when they have trouble reading. The teachers are consistently highly patient in their interactions with students with reading challenges. Recognizing that teachers are essential to teaching and learning, they are the fundamental pillars of knowledge transmission in any country (Ullah et al., 2021).

Meanwhile, indicator 4, the lowest-rated description, utilized different teaching methods and strategies, with a mean score of

4.45 and an SD of 0.89, with the interpretation of To a Great Extent. Students generally believe that teachers use varied modes to teach them and that perhaps there could be a few different modes used. As mentioned, teachers are role models for their students to follow (Getie, 2020). While teachers employ various teaching strategies, there's potential for further development and consistency in their implementation.

3. Regression Analysis: Influence of Factors on Reading Comprehension

Regression analysis was conducted to determine the significance of the factors (parental, home environment, learner-related, and teacher-related factors) in predicting learners' reading comprehension levels.

Table 6. Regression Analysis between Factors Affecting Reading Challenges and Reading Comprehension level

Independent Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig-value	Decision	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
Parental Factors	-0.062	0.099	-0.065	-0.627	0.532	Do not reject the null hypothesis	Not significant
Home Environment Factors	0.002	0.066	0.003	0.031	0.975	Do not reject the null hypothesis	Not significant
Learner-Related Factors	0.079	0.083	0.091	0.943	0.347	Do not reject the null hypothesis	Not significant
Teacher-Related Factors	0.169	0.072	0.203	2.34	0.021	Reject the null hypothesis	Statistically Significant

a. Dependent Variable: reading comprehension level

The results of the multiple linear regression analysis showed different levels of effects of the proposed predictors on students' reading levels. According to the analyses, Parental Factors ($B = -0.062$, $p = 0.532$) did not have a statistically significant effect on reading level. This means that in this model, while controlling for other predictors, parental factors were not significant predictors of students' reading comprehension. This is also in agreement with (Sun'iyah, 2020), which emphasized the balance parents have to be able to offer their children's success with parental and obligation related responsibilities for management and parenting functions. Therefore, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis that Parental Factors had no statistically significant impact on reading levels.

Similarly, the Domain of Home Environment Factors ($B = 0.002$, $p = 0.975$) did not have a statistically significant effect on the reading level. This indicates that the constructs of the home environment, as measured in this study, are not significant predictors of learners' reading comprehension. As a result, the null hypothesis of Home Environment Factors is not rejected. There is a plethora of studies on how parental support and the home literacy environment contribute to motivational and competence outcomes in reading (Altun et al., 2022; Dong et al., 2020; Mudrak et al., 2020; Seneschal, 2006).

The analysis indicated that the Extent of Learner-Related Factors ($B = 0.079$, $p = 0.347$) did not have a statistically significant effect on reading level, indicating that the measured learner-related factors were not statistically significant predictors of reading comprehension in the model. Therefore, the null hypothesis for Learner-Related Factors cannot be rejected.

In this case, the Teacher-Related Factors accounted for a statistically significant positive association with the learners' reading levels ($B = 0.169$, $p = 0.021$). The unstandardized coefficient showed a positive association ($B = 0.169$), indicating a predicted 0.169 unit increase in reading level for a one-unit increase in teacher-related factors, all else being equal. The p-value ($p < .05$) indicated that the null hypothesis for Teacher-Related Factors was rejected. Teacher-related factors are significant indicators of how learners read and comprehend text.

While Parental Factors, Home Environment Factors, and the Extent of Learner-Related Factors do not have significance individually in this model, Teacher-Related Factors reached significance, suggesting that one of the factors that they were analyzing does have an impact on reading comprehension. This supports the research of Cabalo and Cabalo (2019), who recognized the teacher as the top factor impacting students' reading skills. The study concluded that both teachers' education and experience are essential. Moreover, the authors drew a suggestion from their research that implies that teachers with more experience perform better in teaching reading and have more options for strategies and practices to engage their students.

Although the regression analysis showed that home environment factors were insignificant predictors of learners' reading comprehension ($p = 0.975$), it is important to appreciate their practical implications in a learner's academic journey. As stated by Rohimah (2021), home environment plays a crucial role in children's reading development. Lack of parental support, the methods used by parents to educate students at home, students' backgrounds, and students' behaviors significantly contribute to reading difficulties. A home filled with stimulants for reading (e.g., reading materials and quiet

study space) and with the support of parents (e.g., reading and encouraging a child to read) is still an integral part of developing a positive concept as a reader that develops intrinsic interest and motivation for reading. The non-significant results in this study could result from different levels of parental engagement, socio-economic obstacles, or differences in the environmental print provided at home; however, since the past,

research suggests that children who grow up in literacy-rich environments tend to perform better academically in extrapolated time. Thus, while the quantitative analysis revealed no significant relationship, the qualitative and lived experiences of the home environment remained central to children's reading development. This should not be ignored when designing interventions.

4. Specific Reading Practices that Teachers Commonly Use to Help Pupils in Terms of Reading Progress

Table 7. Teacher's Response

Theme	In Vivo Code	Meaning/Interpretation
Reading Practices	"Through the use of reading materials such as books and manuals"	The teacher uses printed resources as the foundation of instruction.
Assessment Methods	Assessment is done through text (written/oral reading) and sometimes recitation"	Assessment is based on oral and written responses, but recitation is not consistently used.
Challenges	"Absenteeism is one of the barriers teachers face nowadays"	Attendance issues hinder reading instruction and learner consistency.
Parent Communication	"Communication with parents or guardians is done through text/messenger"	Teachers communicate primarily through digital tools for efficiency.

4.1 Reading practices used by teachers for pupils

In Vivo Code: "Through the use of reading materials such as books and manuals"

The In Vivo code "Through the use of reading materials such as books and manuals" offers first impressions of the teacher's practices in reading. The terms "books" and "manuals" signal a dependence on more traditional, physical instructional materials or resources in their classroom. "Books" is a general term and could refer to reading materials that could be textbooks, storybooks, or informational books. "Manuals," which the teacher does not specifically define, could refer to various structures of reading resources that are also referred to as "manuals," such as workbooks, instructional materials, or another organization of resources that aids the teacher or students in administering the reading lesson or lesson related to reading. According to Dockx et al. (2020), textbooks also impact the material taught and the didactic signals given by teachers, increasing students' reading comprehension and engagement levels. Since the terms "book" and "manual" were used by the teacher, they see that these readings notably shaped the teacher-research approach. If only more teachers in Bulacan and perhaps the Public Elementary School in Bulacan took on this teacher research and were able to illustrate the different types of books and manuals they used or reasons the teacher selected books or manuals (i.e., fit the curriculum, readily available, believe it was the best fit) along with how the teacher's text/reading practices were integrated into daily reading. Additional studies with a wider sample of teachers in Bulacan and possibly at a Public Elementary School in Bulacan could explore the specific types of books and manuals used,

reasons for selections (e.g., fit with curriculum, availability, and perceived impact), and how the materials fit into daily reading lessons.

4.2 Assessing the effectiveness of the practices

In Vivo Code: "Assessment is done through text (written/oral reading) and sometimes recitation"

The in vivo code table 9, "Assessment is done through text (written/oral reading) and sometimes recitation," offers an important understanding of how teachers assess the effectiveness of their reading practices. The expression "text (written/oral reading)" signifies that the teacher is evaluating the student's ability to interact with and process a written text using writing and oral reading and is likely to evaluate accuracy, fluency, and comprehension. The adverb "sometimes" also indicates that the teacher is assessing comprehension by oral recall and the ability to articulate specific details from the text. However, this was often noted as not being used. The word "sometimes" indicates that recitation was probably not used as a teacher's method for assessing reading comprehension. Educators should seek to find and utilize the best teaching practice for students and not rely on data related to teaching effectiveness but rather on the teaching processes of reading (Shanahan, 2020). Further inquiry could ask what rubrics (or criteria) the teacher used to evaluate written and oral reading, what type of text the teacher used for assessment, how often the teacher used recitation, and what they understood the strengths and weaknesses (if any) of these assessment methods to assess the effectiveness of their reading practices and student development.

4.3 Barriers and challenges faced when implementing such reading practices

In the Vivo Code: "Absenteeism is one of the barriers teachers face nowadays"

The in vivo code from the teacher response, "Absenteeism is one of the barriers teachers face nowadays," explains that pupil absenteeism influences teachers' teaching methodologies and reading approaches. The teacher viewed absenteeism as a possible barrier to learning that "teachers face nowadays" in acknowledging a paradigm of insignificance for learning that presents itself in the historical aspect faced by the school system. As Ansari and Gottfried (2021) highlighted, if learners are often absent, they are missing essential academic skill content, which can lead to poor academic performance compared to their peers. The data also show that 5-15% of elementary learners are chronically absent, so this becomes an important area to study to understand why learners are absent. Absenteeism creates interruptions that deter students' ability to sustain consistent learning about reading instruction and creates obstacles for the teacher to continually develop skills fundamental to reading and learning opportunities about absenteeism. Students frequently absent from school miss important explanations, guided practice, and reading benefits and eventually fall behind their peers. Future work may consider absenteeism in a Public Elementary School in Bulacan, investigate the experience of students' absenteeism, and then consider the topics students will investigate when they

teach their students about their learning when they do not show up for school_ -and what this means (if anything) regarding the impact of attendance on reading.

4.4 Communication with parents about their child's-reading progress

The in Vivo Code: "Communication with parents or guardians is done through text/messenger"

The in vivo code "Communication with parents or guardians is done through text/messenger" shows that the most common form of communication the teacher reports using to inform parents about their child's reading progress was through "texting/messenger." These terms indicate digital communication tools, likely because they are a faster and more convenient choice for both parties. Texting/message communication can enable lequick updates and information-sharing. Leander and Fabella (2020) added that parents and teachers may be better able to communicate with one another, so they have better, updated information on how pupils participate in school activities. However, this may also limit the depth and sophistication of this communication. Further investigation could include how frequently the teacher texted/messaged parents, what types of information might be shared (e.g., child's actual reading level, strengths/weaknesses, suggestions for support/helper activities at home), and whether this method is perceived as effective in increasing parental influence and involvement in their child's reading development.

5. Strategies, Habits and Resources for Supporting Children's Reading Development and Addressing Challenges.

Table 8. *Parents Interview responses*

Main Theme	Subthemes	Codes
Parents use various strategies, habits, and resources to support their child's reading development.	Availability of Printed Materials	Books, pocketbooks, comics, charts
	Electronic Resources for Reading	Cellphones, tablets, YouTube, Google
	Motivation Strategies for Reading	Setting reading before playtime
		Giving food, rewards, time management
		Allowing self-directed reading
	Communication with teacher	Messenger, group chat
Visiting school, casual conversations with teachers		

Table 8 presents a thematic analysis of the structured interview responses of the parents, which supports the quantitative findings of the study. The sub-theme identified showed what available material, resources, and strategies parents used to help pupils in their reading progress. The first subtheme highlights the use of books, pocketbooks, comics, and charts as one of the main resources of parents as materials in helping pupils in their

reading progress. The responses regarding this subtheme are presented below:

"We don't have books, but we have charts that we stick on the wall, and my child often watches YouTube."
Parent 1

"Uhm, we have pocket books and comic books for children." Parent 2

"Of course, I know that they are usually with their mother. I have seen them reading books, and I know that those books came from my spouse's sibling, whose children went to a private school. The books were given to them, and now they are reading them." Parent 3

"Yes, we have." Parent 4

This response shows a wide choice of available material parents used to help pupils. Recommending books and engaging in discussions of readings also support engagement in reading and improved performance even in early adolescence (Baker, Citation 2003; Xia et al., 2019). One parent answered that they do not have books at home, but that they have charts that can affect children's exposure to literature. This also shows the limitations of the materials used by parents, which may affect the variety of choices for pupil reading.

Parents use electronic resources, specifically cellphones and tablets, as well as applications such as YouTube and Google, to help their children read. Gadgets are not only used by teachers, the community, and students; in today's world, students are already using them. Smartphones, notebook computers, cellphones, and other gadgets are widely used (Walyyunita A'yun et al., 2021). Some parents allow their child to use electronic devices to find and obtain the information they need, while some parents do not allow their child to use gadgets for reading, as they see them as a distraction to the child's learning. Despite this, electronic resources are seen as valuable tools for gathering information and supplementing traditional reading.

"When my kids need something for school, they use their cellphones. And you know, since Google searching is popular, we just look things up online." Parent 1

"Uhm, he/she doesn't use a phone for reading because there are many distractions there" Parent 2

"Just a phone; he just watches YouTube there." Parent 3

"Of course, a cell phone. We also bought a tablet where my children read." Parent 4

"Yes, we have" Parent 5

The responses show the mixed reactions of the respondents, where some of them find that electronic resources can be valuable resources that will help their children's learning progress. Some view electronic resources as distractions in children's learning.

Parents apply different strategies to motivate and engage their children's reading. Some of them say that they are giving their children rewards, such as food and other things they want, in line with the findings of Caliskan and Ulas (2022), which show

that parental involvement in pupils' reading progress is highly related to students' motivation. It also highlighted the extrinsic motivation in which pupils or individuals are controlled by their demands, rewards, and social needs. Some also say that they set boundaries between play and reading, which allow their children to read before playtime. Others have said that they allow their children to read independently.

"When they get home before they go out to play, I tell them to read first and finish their assignments right away so they can get them done quickly." Parent 1

"By giving him/her the food he/she wants to eat." Parent 2

"I do not force my children; they are still young. But my children are well-behaved, and they know when they have assignments—they will do it." Parent 3

"In giving them rewards and repetitions, that is it. Ah, and time management." Parent 4

The responses above show the answers of parents under the question "How do you keep your child motivated and engaged in reading?" Showing the variety of different strategies and methods of parents to motivate their children to read.

Parents of instructional and frustrated readers use various means of communication, including group chats and face-to-face meetings, to monitor their children's progress. Anub (2023) emphasized that the success of alternative teaching approaches relies heavily on the support of the community, which shows how parents take an active role in monitoring their children's reading progress through various communication methods. This indicated that the parents of the respondents were proactive in seeking information about their reading abilities. While some parents prefer the convenience of digital communication, others opt for personal interactions to ensure that they will be informed about the development of their child's progress.

"If I'm not chatting in the group chat, sometimes I go to the school to find out any updates about my kids, just things like that." Parent 1

"I talk to my child's teacher to find out about his/her progress or performance in school." Parent 2

"Most of the time through Messenger, but sometimes during the time when I need to get the card in the school." Parent 3

"Of course, as a father, I drop off and pick up my children. When I see their teacher, I sometimes ask about their performance, and the teacher says they are doing well." Parent 4

The table above indicates that the parents' responses about communicating with their child's teacher were often flexible

through digital responses as well as face-to-face communication.

In conclusion, parents' answers in this interview varied in the strategy they used to support their children's reading progress, with both traditional printed materials and gadgets. Gadgets have made their way into the lives of all ages, including the students. The wide accessibility of these gadgets affects students' inclination toward reading. Anggriani (2020) determined that gadgets impact students' reading inclination in a statistically significant manner. The motivation parents used as a strategy varies with the structured routines and rewards they give to pupils. Parents' communication with teachers is key to monitoring and improving pupils' reading progress. Be it in person or online, parents' monitoring of their child's progress is important. With this, it is clear that a parent's supportive reading environment requires significant effort in accessing material and even communicating with teachers.

6. Action Plan for Addressing Reading Challenges

This section presents two action plans intended to ignite students' love for reading, address their reading difficulties, and provide appropriate support and guidance through collaborative action among teachers, students, and parents. As assured by the results of this study, the plans will seek to address all reading difficulties experienced by students directly, particularly students flagged at the "instructional" and "frustration" levels in the PHIL-IRI post-assessment.

These two comprehensive plans fit well with ideas contained in Duke, Ward, and Pearson (2021) by supporting the cognitive

factors of reading, which include phonological awareness, print concepts, and oral language comprehension using strategies such as read-aloud (Cervetti, 2020; Swanson et al., 2011). By using differentiated instruction methods, assessing and continuously monitoring reading at home and in learning environments, peer support, and parental help, these plans seek to engage voluntary reading as much as possible to provide the most helpful reading progress with Grade 4-6 struggling readers.

1. Home and School: Collaboration for Reading Success
Purpose: The purpose of this plan was to help children ignite love for reading. It also helps children in their reading challenges and provides proper support and nourishment, fostering involvement and collaboration from teachers and parents.

Objective: To support the development of reading skills of students with reading difficulties by participating in reading activities at home and school for one school quarter equivalent to 10 whole weeks, establishing a positive reading environment and routine, with the partnership of teachers and parents.

Target Group:

- Learners: Grade 4-6 pupils with reading difficulties according to their PHIL-IRI post conference test.
- Stakeholders: Teachers and Parents of pupils with reading difficulties.

Table 9. Home and School: Collaboration for Reading Success

Week	Activity	Persons Involved	Description	Action Taken
Week 1	Initial Reading Assessment and Reflection	Teacher, Pupils, and Parents	For this activity, this will serve as the initial assessment of the teacher to pupils. This will help the teacher to know who will be involved in this intervention.	This will happen at the beginning of the session. For pupils: The teacher will create a short assessment for pupils to know their status. For parents: The teacher will ask the parent to create a reflection focusing on the children's status at home.
Week 2	Reading Mission	Teacher and Parents	This will serve as training and initial planning for everyone who is participating in the intervention.	The teacher will initiate a webinar or seminar for parents. The topics should be about how parents can help their child in developing the child's reading skills and comprehension.
Week 3-4	Word Hunt	Teacher and Pupils.	For two weeks, the teacher will establish the pupils' awareness of their environment.	The teacher will provide letters and their sounds, such as /e/, /s/, and /t/, and the pupils will hunt objects around them that start with these sounds.

Week 5-6	Book Haven	Teacher and Pupils.	For two weeks, the teacher will focus on establishing the pupils' desire for reading. This will also help students become independent.	The teacher will create a designated reading zone for the pupils. It can be in the corner of the classroom, where bookshelves full of reading materials are placed. Teachers can also put blankets and pillows to make reading more comfortable for pupils.
Week 7-8	Family as book buddy	Teacher, parent, and pupil.	For two weeks, the reading session will be conducted at home and guided by the parents. The parents were the students' book buddies. This creates a bond and connection between parents and pupils at home. This will also make the pupils feel supported by their parents.	The parents choose a story in which they can read together with their child. Parents should ensure that the child is participating in the narration with their guidance. During these weeks the parents should update the teacher about the pupils' progress.
Week 9	Shared Reading Memory	Teacher and pupils.	For this week, sharing of experience and a read-aloud session will happen at school.	The pupils are required to share their experience about the different activities they had from the previous week. After that the teacher will ask students to read aloud together with their classmates.
Week 10	Reading Assessment, Reflection, and Awarding.	Teacher, Pupils, and Parents	For this week, assessment and evaluation will happen. Awarding of certificates will also take place during this time.	This will happen at the end of the session. For pupils: The teacher will create a short assessment for pupils to monitor their progress. For parents: The teacher will ask the parent to create a reflection focusing on the children's progress at home. The teacher will give certificates to parents and pupils who have participated in the intervention.

This action plan emphasizes shared responsibility and collaboration between parents and teachers for the reading development of pupils. This action plan is a 10-week program to develop and enhance the reading ability of Grade 4-6 pupils identified by their schools as having reading difficulties. This is a structured design that emphasizes the importance of collaboration between parents and teachers to support their children's reading development. The action plan includes activities that will assess the reading level of students, followed by focused reading instruction, reading practice at home, continued evaluation of reading progress, and recognition and motivation to succeed. Supporting children in their reading challenges is important in creating a consistent and well-rounded plan while maintaining the importance of fostering a love for reading and developing solid reading skills, which ultimately will drive higher academic outcomes for the students. (Rand & Morrow, 2021).

2. Personalized Literacy Mentorship programs

Purpose: To develop intermediate reading skills in students through differentiated reading that meets particular students' reading needs with Parent-Teacher-Student Collaboration. Children help other children as peer mentors and engage in shared reading and learning activities to improve their reading skills. This project sought to help learners combat reading difficulties and bring the community together through parental and peer participation.

Objective: To improve students' reading ability by personalizing readings using Personalized Reading Maps based on students' reading levels and preferences. This also promotes family participation and student cooperation. Therefore, students feel more comfortable discussing literature. This also provides opportunities for reflective reading and boosts vocabulary and comprehension.

Target

Learners: Intermediate learners with reading challenges.

Group:

Table 10. *Personalized Literacy Mentorship Program*

Week	Activity	Persons Involved	Description
Week 1	Organization and creation of Personalized Reading Maps and Mentor Matching	Teachers, Students, Mentors	Teachers assess the reading capabilities and interests of the students to create personalized Reading Maps, a personalized outline of specific books and activities to be pursued. Students are paired with “Literacy Mentors,” fellow students, and peers who are excellent readers.
Week 2	First Mentoring Session	Student, Mentor, Parent, Teacher	The student and literacy mentor meet to read and analyze a selected story. Mentors guide the students in comprehension and vocabulary while parents observe and take notes on their children’s performance to be reported to the teachers.
Week 3	Read and Reflect	Student, Parent, Teacher	Students read assigned passages at home based on the suggestions of the reading map. Parents fill out a “Reading Reflection Journal” with their children, which their teacher monitors to track progress.
Week 4	Second Mentor Session	Student, Mentor, Parent, Teacher	The mentor and student meet, focusing on vocabulary building and recognizing new words. Parents act as observers and take notes of the new words to reinforce their use of them at home.
Week 5	Parent-Mentor Discussion	Teacher, Parent, Mentor	Parents and mentors discuss their child's progress and strategies. This may also be a time for Mentors to support their children's progress.
Week 6	Third Mentor Session	Student, Mentor, Parent, Teacher	Mentors and students meet once again, focusing on deepening learners' comprehension. Parents are advised to observe and encouraged to ask questions to support their children's learning.
Week 7	Final Home Reading and Reflection	Student, Parent, Teacher	Students complete their readings and final assignments on their Reading Map. Students, parents, and teachers review the reading journal and discuss what the student learned and how the student developed in reading.
Week 8	Collective Progress Report and Review	Teacher, Student, Parent, Mentor	Students share their reading experiences with their peers and discuss their favorite books, along with their current projects. Mentors, parents, and teachers discuss the overall progress and the next steps that may be taken for continued developmental reading.

The Personalized Literacy Mentorship Program revolves around the individual needs of students and seeks to support intermediate learners with reading difficulties in improving their reading skills, reading comprehension, and vocabulary. This program uses personalized mentorship and strong collaboration between learners, parents, and teachers. The program uses personalized mentorship with learning plans, peer mentoring, and parental involvement to establish a complete learning environment that supports developmental reading. Reading proficiency is a foundational skill that affects a child's academic success regardless of the subject area. Becoming proficient in reading in early elementary school also serves as a good predictor of later academic performance and overall success in life (Mulcahy et al., 2019). Within the extended eight-week program, learners work through personalized activities aligned with their Reading Maps, which include specific activities that support how each learner learns and grows with the support of their peers and parents to

ensure that they receive direction and gentle nudges in their learning.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings allow us to draw conclusions regarding the reading challenges experienced by intermediate learners at a Public Elementary School in Bulacan. Based on this research, the results of the Phil-IRI post-conference also pointed out that many learners were stuck with frustrating instructional levels, indicating that intervention is necessary and supporting the identified need for some intervention in mixed-ability classrooms with differentiation for various reading needs.

Even though learners reported that parental and home environment factors contributed positively to the learning environment, the home environment factors were not statistically significant with reading comprehension levels. Learner-related factors, such as motivation and preparedness, were reported very highly by pupils, but were again not

statistically significant with reading comprehension in the regression analysis. Therefore, the null hypothesis could not be rejected for the home environment and learner-related factors, meaning that the home environment and learner-related variables did not significantly contribute to learners' reading comprehension in this study. Although the home environment factor was not statistically significant, it was recognized that it was practically important in learners' reading development, which is supported by earlier literature findings.

Conversely, teacher-related factors were the only significant predictors of learners' RC levels. Based on the regression analysis, we concluded that teacher-related support, which included the availability of reading material, individualized support, and appropriate teaching practices, made a meaningful and positive contribution to learners' performance. The null hypothesis for teacher-related factors was rejected. This reiterates the importance of teachers and states that building teacher capacity and support systems is an essential way to improve learners' reading challenges.

The qualitative data provided by the parents and teachers reflected and supported the quantitative data. Parents reported a mix of print and digital resources, using motivating strategies and contacting the teachers involved in their children's reading. The teacher reported using traditional instructional resources, assessing students' reading, and talking with parents but also highlighted challenges in helping readers, such as attendance.

Overall, the study concluded that multiple contextual and individual factors influence a learner's reading experience; however, when looking at a learner's reading comprehension outcomes, the quality and nature of teacher support were most influential for intermediate learners in this study.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is recommended that teachers begin to differentiate reading instruction to cater to the needs of instructional- and frustration-level readers, using a combination of traditional and alternative reading sources appropriate for learners' needs per Phil-IRI outcomes as well as instructional practices.

School administrators should provide teachers with professional development opportunities regularly related to how to manage reading difficulties, using multiple strategies of instruction, and working towards developing better assessment tools, as the only significant predictor of reading comprehension in the regression analysis was teacher-related issues.

One area of practice that needs to be addressed is starting and maintaining reading corners, having access to appropriate-level reading materials for learners in every classroom, and encouraging independent reading. Notably, since learners indicated that they had limited opportunities to access low-level reading materials, classrooms with structured reading corners were highly valued.

It is recommended that parents receive strategies to develop a structure around reading at home, and to read with the child, as demonstrated in both the quantitative responses, as well as the interview data, despite the lack of statistical significance regarding parental factors in the regression model.

Communication between parents and teachers about monitoring learners' progress should be enhanced through consistent digital platforms along with scheduled face-to-face meetings to monitor learning and provide support strategies, as portrayed in both teacher and parent interviews.

The plans for action, like 'Home and School Collaboration for Reading Success' and 'Personalized Literacy Mentorship Program', will need to be piloted to understand their practicable success in overcoming reading problems in real educational practice.

Future researchers should also consider the additional variables of differing socio-economic status, digital literacy, and multilingual backgrounds and encourage more teachers and parent participants for sampling and contextual variation.

Authors Note

Serina Amper, Angel Lhaine C. Arnado, Jonamy Buslon, Jemelyn D.C. Robles, Marielle Coleen D.R. Saguid, and Joseline M. Santos, Ph.D., Richelle C. Castro, and Remelie R. Robles, Ed.D, LPT are affiliated with Bulacan State University, Malolos, Bulacan 3000, Philippines.

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